

AUTOMATIC SEGMENTATION AND 3D RECONSTRUCTION OF PATIENT- SPECIFIC CAROTID ARTERY BY USING ULTRASOUND IMAGES

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Abstract:

The main purpose of this study is automatic segmentation and 3D reconstruction of patient-specific carotid artery affected by atherosclerosis. The presented approach includes a combination of deep learning techniques for automatic segmentation of longitudinal and transversal ultrasound (US) images, and meshing techniques for 3D reconstruction of patient-specific model using segmented regions of interest as the input. The US dataset of carotid arteries, which contains data obtained from several clinical centers, is used and our model has shown robustness and reliability in processing heterogeneous images as input. All US images underwent the preprocessing and annotation. The obtained results show high accuracy in region detection and segmentation (Precision - 0.92, Recall - 0.92, Dice coefficient (F1-score) - 0.93). The automatic extraction of US features gives the specific segmentation of individual patient-specific anatomy, while the reconstructed 3D models can be used for further computational simulations of atherosclerosis progression and analysis of individual patients.

Key words: deep learning, image segmentation, 3D reconstruction, finite element mesh.

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